

Blockchain technology: principles, applications, and challenges

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Abstract— With the exponential advancement in blockchain technology, blockchain brought considerable change to businesses and technology, making a tamper-proof and decentralised approach that can verify and track transactions. Blockchain brings in data integrity, transparency and privacy, which helps multiple fields achieve a decentralised approach. This paper will explore the principles, application and challenges of blockchain technology.

Keywords— *decentralized, blockchain, transaction, applications, privacy, transparency, ledger*

I. INTRODUCTION

For the past few decades, online transactions have become more prominent, which people and companies capitalised on by creating a digital payment method centralised and controlled by third-party companies. A centralised approach can cause problems when a hacker gains access to the system because the centralised approach contains all the data in one place. However, blockchain technology uses a decentralised approach with no third parties involved in the transaction and data. An example of a decentralised digital currency is bitcoin, developed by Satoshi Nakamoto [4]. Bitcoin overcomes the digital transaction problems by using Proof-of-Work, an algorithm that adds blocks every 10 minutes, thus restricting votes per entity [1]. Bitcoin was the first application created in blockchain technology [12].

According to AK Jena and SP Dash [1], blockchain has permission and permission-less rules categorised based on permission strategy. A permission blockchain is a private blockchain, where approved users can only publish blocks, and a permissionless blockchain is public, where anyone within that network can publish blocks.

What is blockchain? Blockchain principles give a fundamental meaning to blockchain technology and provide basic information. A blockchain is a cluster of transactions known as blocks, and a blockchain is a group of blocks [5]. The blockchain contains cryptographic concepts such as asymmetric key cryptography, hashing and digital signatures. The blockchain components are transactions, hashing, blocks and addresses [1]; this would need a separate discussion below. This paper will also discuss the challenges of blockchain, that it would need a considerable amount of effort to solve what could slow down blockchain technology innovation—loss of privacy, scalability, sustainability and attacks. Blockchain applications show an immense improvement in many sectors and continue to help many people with privacy and sharing.

II. BLOCKCHAIN PRINCIPLES

A. Decentralised

Blockchain is a peer-to-peer, where no third party controls the transactions; all the nodes contain the distributed ledger

(ledger is responsible for keeping records of the transactions), which prevents people from monopolising or compromising the network from validating transactions [8] and removes the single point of vulnerability [13]. Blockchain allows robustness; if a block is changed, the server will not stop the transaction and copy from a different peer as other peers in the blockchain have a copy of the transaction [8].

The problem with blockchain implementing distributed ledgers is efficiency and scalability issues. The more trust added to the blockchain entities, the more centralised the process will become, but the more increase in efficiency in the blockchain will become [2].

B. Anonymity and privacy

Blockchain allows the user to comment and post whilst anonymously, achieved by having a pair of randomly generated keys where the user selects one to be a pseudonym and the other to sign the transaction, which is traceable [8]. This type of anonymity is called pseudo-anonymous.

C. Transparency

Public blockchain visibility shows all its data and allows users to connect to the network. Permissioned blockchain also allows users to connect and download the blockchain's contents, verified by the user [8]. The user and the provider are anonymous whilst being able to post and comment on the blockchain [1].

III. BLOCKCHAIN COMPONENTS

A. Consensus mechanism

The consensus mechanism is a process where a decision supports the network and where the network user will agree to make the network better [1]. The consensus model shows the process of adding a block to the blockchain, which is a node that will need to solve a cryptographic puzzle that will require large amounts of computation power, and once the puzzle is solved, the network will then verify the block and added into the blockchain [1].

B. Transactions

Block contains zero to many transactions [1]. A transaction in a blockchain represents an exchange between two entities [1]. Transactions keep the information recorded in the blockchain, and the information of the transaction are price, asset, user and verifies the transaction across all nodes [1]. Narayanan and others stated that the transaction contains the input and output of the transaction, the sender's public key, the sender's address and the digital signature [6].

C. Hashing method

Hashing is considered an essential component of blockchain technology as hashing functions as a cryptographic mechanism [1]. Hashing is where the data is converted into a fixed size, even if the data is larger than the

proposed size. The data input is either a text, image or file, and the output will be an alpha-numeric string. The hashing method ensures that the user's data is transmitted and not changed. If the data is slightly changed, the hash value will change. The hashing technique creates a security property for the blockchain, and one of the properties is that it is not possible to compute the input based on the output of the data, which is called pre-image resistance [1]. The other properties mentioned by AK Jena and SP Dash are second pre-image resistant: based on the input provided, the second input that generates the output is impossible to compute, and the other property is collision-resistant, which means that the two inputs are complicated to generate the same hash output [1].

A nonce is considered an essential factor in proof-of-work, and it is an abbreviation for "a number only used once". It completes proof-of-work by containing a random number, which combines with the block to change the hash output [1]. Blockchain miners will try to solve the nonce, which allows the miners to receive cryptocurrency [1].

D. Blocks

A block has a block header that contains the block's metadata, and the block body contains all valid transactions [7]. The implementation of the blockchain can determine the metadata of the block [1]. The hash from the previous block will chain the newly formed block to form a blockchain; if a single block is changed, the rest of the blocks will change, resulting in a different hash, which makes it easier to find out that the data was changed [1].

E. Addresses

The address is data in the transaction point between the sender and receiver, and the data is short and in alphanumeric characters [1]. Not all addresses are the same in a different blockchain due to a different implementation to obtain the address. The blockchain users will require to store their private keys in a safeguarded area, such as a wallet, which can keep the user's public key and address [1].

IV. TYPES OF BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain has many types and has evolved over the years. Blockchain continues to grow further and create more opportunities.

A. Private blockchain

Private blockchains are not open to the public and are only open to blockchain members. The blockchain members that are participating have a shared ledger [9].

B. Semi-private blockchain

Semi-private blockchains are partially open to the public to participate, and some parts are private only to the members of a group or an organisation [9].

C. Public blockchain

There is no owner for the ledger in the public blockchain, and it is publicly available for anyone to participate. The distributed consensus mechanism decides to maintain a copy of the ledger on the user's local node [9]. Some users may not gain any involvement in the decision process [9].

D. Distributed ledger

The distributed ledger is distributed among participants and connected without any breaks. The ledger can spread among private or public organisations [9].

E. Permissioned ledger

The permission ledger does not use a consensus mechanism and uses an agreement protocol to share among trusted participants [9].

V. APPLICATIONS OF BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain applications bring advantages because they open new fields that allow blockchain to improve. Blockchain applications support governments and business sectors such as E-voting, renting a car and others [1]. Blockchain is not restricted only to these domains, and many researchers are figuring out how to fit blockchain into other fields.

A. Blockchain in finance

Blockchain supports finance, which combines with technology to help automate financial services, remove third parties, and allow faster transaction service [1]. The term used to describe finance and technology is FinTech [1]. Many finance services can use blockchain to automate, such as insurance, which automates claim functions by verifying the coverage, is risk-free and can detect fraudulent claims [1].

B. Blockchain in internet of things (IoT)

The application of blockchain on the internet of things is massive due to the potential blockchain used in smart devices and cloud services, which are few potentials in IoT [1]. For instance, healthcare can gather a vast amount of information is generated and the information is stored centrally, and managing becomes impossible; this is where blockchain can change the system by making the company, the patients and the staff become the users of the blockchain and then managing it [1]. IoT has a central server to manage its security and other essential tasks, which could pose a problem when hacked; a solution is to use blockchain technology to store the data decentralised [15].

C. Blockchain in education

The application of blockchain in education has not fully progressed [1]. However, few ideas have the potential for achieving academic feats. The current idea is having identity management, which can improve and create reliable information to provide evidence for the user achievements. Blockchain can provide certificates, which further support the user identity proof and achievements [1].

D. Blockchain in e-voting

Blockchain supports voting by allowing voters to cast their votes online securely. The reason is that blockchain is tamper-proof and can avoid counterfeits of votes [1]. Thus, making votes affirm and being able to go anywhere whilst voting is suited to anybody. Voters will also have a sense of privacy when using blockchain to vote so that only the vote is known to the voter, which can prevent peer pressure or even negative votes [2]. However, there is a known issue where blockchain can allow real-time tallying, which can easily sway voters to change their votes [2].

E. Blockchain in supply chains

The application of blockchain in supply chains can reduce transaction costs and increase transaction speed [1]. If a customer wants a refund because the product is faulty, the blockchain will order and trace the product to refund the customer. The whole process of the supply chain is like the blockchain process, creating an opportunity to replace the

whole process, making the process faster for both the supplier and buyer [1].

F. Blockchain in healthcare

As described in the internet of things, the healthcare industry gathers many data, and the patients do not control their data [10]. Blockchain solves the problem by storing the patient data in the organisation's internal database and allowing smart contracts to allow patients to manage their medical data and control who can see it [10].

1) Clinical adjudication

Clinical adjudication requires a large amount of data gained from collecting data on a piece of new equipment or new drug effectiveness. Blockchain technology allows everyone from the stakeholder to access any data on the new device or new drug, which will prevent manufacturer's claims about the potency and effectiveness of the new drug or device. Blockchain technology allows authentication for any data in the bookkeeping to be easily reached by all the stakeholders [10].

2) Claims adjudication

Claims adjudication happens when the client submits a medical claim to the insurance company to determine if the client is eligible for the payment. The healthcare industry suffers from these claims due to false claims and inefficiencies in billing [10]. Blockchain technology can make it easier for the client to apply through the blockchain automatically, making the process much faster due to smart contracts. Smart contracts prevent explaining the situation twice or more, which reduces the time taken when not taking the legal language route [10].

G. Intrusion detection with blockchain

The previous paper, "Intrusion detection systems: A survey and taxonomy", where discuss intrusion detection system (IDS) have to protect against growing cyber-threats and blockchain technology will be able to develop IDS by allowing to share detection data with other organisations without worrying about the trust factor between them [14]. However, the companies gathering a large amount of data is a problem; it can degrade the security and detect regular routines as a threat, which will result in a failed IDS [14].

VI. CHALLENGES OF BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain technology has many advantages. However, there are limits to blockchain technology. The challenges of blockchain technology are loss of privacy, selfish mining, and the blockchain's scalability [1]. Another problem is the marching time of a new vulnerability or a malicious attack.

A. Loss of privacy

The loss of privacy occurs when the user transaction is on the blockchain, which is trackable, as all the transactions and balances are publicly available. However, the blockchain's user identity is not exposed as the public key cryptography maintains the identity of the user [1].

B. Scalability

The transactions in the blocks are getting larger every day, causing the nodes to collect and validate every transaction in the blockchain, which can take a considerable number of resources and time. The blockchain can restrict the number of transactions in a block, but this may not be enough to handle the large amount of data required to process in real-time [1].

Also, blockchain will need to handle the other three tasks whilst handling the enormous amount of data contained in the transaction: consensus mechanism, signature verification and redundancy [16].

C. Sustainability

The sustainability of blockchain technology in terms of energy consumption is generally rare as there is hardly any recent research based on it [12]. However, bitcoin publications about energy consumption and sustainability have numerous researches, which makes determining blockchain technology as a whole would be complicated [12]. Another point is that determining each user's consumption on the distributed networks would be extremely difficult as their hardware and the amount of effort given to the networks are unknown [12]. However, one way to determine the energy consumption is by calculating the total hash rate and multiplying the minimum energy consumption per hash [12].

Another sustainability challenge that arises from blockchain technology is the use of computer resources that are required to run the network and to be able to mine the blocks [12]. A massive shortage of semiconductors caused by many miners buying new components to increase their computer resources led to an increase in graphic card prices, causing the market to slow down [12].

VII. ATTACKS IN BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain technology provides a decent amount of protection against malicious attacks. However, a new device or implementation will always have a vulnerability.

A. Selfish mining attack

Selfish mining is where the miner secretly keeps his blocks unpublished, and the block is only published when the requirement meets its target. Other miners would then agree to the chain; this chain is longer than the openly available one, making the other miners lose resources on the chain, leading to abandonment later on. The selfish miner achieves their reward due to the method used [1].

B. Data malleability attack

A data malleability attack is where the attacker intercepts and modifies the contents of the transaction or message, which creates an undesirable property and makes the original transaction invalid [3]. The effects of the malleability attack are applications crash, incorrect balance and a deadlock, which stops transactions [3].

C. Eclipse attack

The eclipse attack is where the attacker excludes a specific user from the blockchain and obscures their view on the network, allowing the attacker to prepare other attacks or cause disruption to the network; the attacker achieves this by creating an artificial environment around that node [11].

D. Sybil attack

Sybil attack is where the attacker identifies as multiple users and floods a network, allowing the attacker to control the network. In some cases, Sybil attacks may slow down the network and create a new protocol, affecting other honest users [10].

E. 51% attack

51% attack is where the miners on the blockchain network by 51% on smaller networks, allowing the attacker to gain

50% or more hashing power, as more extensive networks are harder to happen [10].

F. Parity MultiSig wallet attack

Parity MultiSig wallet attack is where an attacker hacked a parity customer wallet, which sent two malicious transactions, the first one is to obtain the owner of MultiSig, and the second transaction is to move the funds [10]. The attacker then started a killing procedure and stole \$77 million [10].

G. The DAO attack

The attack is considered the most consequential exploit in the cryptocurrency record [10]. It was an automated crowdfunding cryptocurrency and raised around 12.7 million ethers [10]. An attacker found a vulnerability in the code, which allowed the attacker to send a small amount of ether and request a withdrawal; this was a repetitive task created by the attacker. The attacker then draws around \$70 million from using the technique [10].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Blockchain technology has transformed many industries with its properties such as a decentralised approach, data integrity, transparency and anonymity. Blockchain technology started with bitcoin and has gone to other applications, which helps support online trust, gaining a chance to improve where it could not have done before.

Blockchain technology advances many industries, creating many opportunities and privacy for many users. However, there are some issues around blockchain technology, such as energy consumption, loss of privacy and scalability, which shows that blockchain technology would still need more improvements to help the current fields and other fields. This paper discusses the principles, applications and challenges of blockchain technology. It separates it into different topics: blockchain principles, components of blockchain, types of blockchain, applications of blockchain and challenges of blockchain, which allows covering current solutions and problems surrounding blockchain technology.

This paper has assessed blockchain technology applications and threats, proving that further research would benefit blockchain technology more, which will protect against zero-day vulnerabilities as more industries are competing, thus improving the security flaws found through innovations.

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